

Animation as a Transmedia Catalyst

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This paper examines the place and the role of animation - understood as the art of artificially creating the illusion of movement frame by frame - in the history of media. I would like to argue that animation plays an active role in the deployment of transmedia and the advent of new media, such as video games.

The question here is: how does animation act as a catalyst for transmedia, precipitating the interactive future of the media?

This question raises the underlying issue of the appropriate methodologies to capture such a protean object. To understand the development of animation and its interactions with other media (cinema, television, video games, Internet, etc.), we need to adopt a perspective transmedia and transdisciplinary perspective.

Animation is a sector apart from the film industry. It has been a long time considered as “children's animated cartoon”, and so it has been marginalized within the *Film Studies*. Animation constitutes consequently an art world (the art of creating movement frame by frame) within a larger art world (cinema). Yet this small art world provides fertile ground for thinking about a transnational history of the media: human and aesthetic circulations, unfolding within a relatively small field of actors, are easier to trace.

Long marginalized by film studies, animation is now theorized as a "cultural meta-series" integrating cinema, and seems to be an omnipresent medium embedded at the heart of all other visual media: in web interfaces and network communications (via gifs) as in video games.

In this paper, I'm going to restrict myself to examining three aspects of the interaction between animation and other media, corresponding to three distinct methodologies : a case study of Walt Disney's career, and his implementation of a transmedia economy ; a media archaeology of visual forms and the circulation of aesthetic paradigms of animated cinema, illustrated by an analysis of the video game *Donkey Kong* ; and, to conclude, a theoretical reflection on the relationship between animation and interactivity, questioning the way in which animation seems to have spread to other media.

1. Animation: an art form developed at the crossroads of media, contributing to the emergence of transmedia

The transmedia development of animation can first be considered by studying the social trajectories of its actors. The interactions between animation and other media unfold through the careers of specific individuals, who have circulated between media since the beginnings of the history of animation.

First of all, I would like to briefly mention the transmedia careers of animation pioneers such as Émile Cohl and Winsor McCay, who brought the press cartoon to the cinema screen: the institution of the cartoon as an aesthetic form and economic sector is based on a media transfusion. Émile Cohl was a cartoonist, photographer and game designer. He was long considered the father of French cartooning, and helped found the cartoon industry in the USA. Winsor McCay worked as a fairground cartoonist before becoming a press cartoonist, animating his drawings, and then working in live entertainment. The cartoon industry itself developed as a media transfusion from the press cartoon to the cinema screen.

I will then focus on a case study: Walt Disney's impact on the entertainment industry, to show how, in return, animation contributes to the emergence of transmedia industries. In the 1930s, Disney initiated the logic of derivative products through merchandising and the creation of comic strips based on cartoons. In the 1950s, the Disney empire branched out into television and the Disneyland theme park, basing its business model on transmedia synergies. Animation, which had its origins in press cartoons, comic strips and the fairground world, returned to this medium, modifying its form.

2. The aesthetic influence of animation across media borders

The history of the transmedia circulation of animation can then be written at the aesthetic level of the life of forms. It's no longer a question of studying the career of a creator navigating from one medium to another, but of looking at the works produced, to show how they reify the technical and aesthetic exchanges between different media.

The first cartoon creators came from the amusement park and the press. These social trajectories determine the aesthetics of the cartoon. The characters of the first cartoons came from comic strips (*Little Nemo*, *The Pieds Nickelés*, *The Katzenjammer Kids...*), and spoke in phylacteries, while the cartoon was presented as a cinema of attractions, inspired in its movements and its relationship to the audience by the physical sensations produced in the amusement park universe.

If a transmedia logic presides over the emergence of theatrical animation, the principles and aesthetic forms produced by animated cinema, in return, program the emergence of new interactive media. In this part, I will be focusing on how animated films, and cartoons in particular, are proving decisive for video games - visually, technically, narratively and kinesthetically, in the way they determine certain game mechanics. A study of *Donkey Kong* (Nintendo, 1980) illustrates this web of influence.

On a visual level, I will be looking at how the game's limited animations extend the limited animations of UPA (United Production of America). This studio, founded in 1945 by Disney dissidents following the strikes of 1941, made a radical break with Disney's aesthetic, proposing a new aesthetic that was decisive in the transition from theatrical cartoon to television cartoon. The development of limited animation thus seems to have been determined by the development of the cold medium of television and video.

Technically, the game's display is based on the sprite principle, which in turn incorporates principles developed by the cartoon industry, in particular the use of transparency and multiplane.

In narrative terms, *Donkey Kong* was initially conceived as an adaptation of *Popeye*, whose structure it adopts: Popeye must rescue Olive from the hands of Bluto, while Jumpman (the protagonist of *Donkey Kong*) must rescue a princess from Donkey Kong. The very setting of the diegesis, with its scaffolding, is explicitly inspired by certain episodes in the *Popeye* series.

In addition to this spatial layout, cartoons also influence game mechanics, determining the rhythms and movements used in video games. The principle of die & retry, for example, and the staged repetition of death, seem to come straight out of cartoon logic, just as the principle of power up, which reverses the balance of power between protagonist and antagonists, is inspired by Popeye's spinach.

3. Animation, between hand and machine: an interactive catalyst

Animation has accompanied the emergence of new media not only in terms of aesthetics, but also in terms of structure. Fundamentally, animation is a reappropriation by the hand of the work of image production that cinema usually delegates to the machine. It reintroduces the hand into an automated process, and this "return of the hand" produces a certain relationship to the spectacle. In this way, animated cinema tends to produce a spectator who actively participates in the spectacle. Animation has never ceased to encourage the spectacle to become a space for play, a relationship to the image that ultimately seems to contaminate all media.

Cartoons, in fact, with their many ways of addressing the audience, and their aesthetic of shock, invite the public to enter the image. Winsor McCay's shows, for example, made this penetration into the

image a reality, with the artist literally entering the screen. In the 1920s, Fleischer Studio's *Screen-Songs* created a form of cinematic karaoke, inviting the audience to sing along to the lyrics on the screen.

In the second half of the 20th century, television animation extended this participatory relationship with the image: Marsha Kinder's work has shown how television cartoons foster a playful, interactive relationship with the image among children, preparing them « for full participation in this new age of interactive multimedia— specifically, by linking interactivity with consumerism¹. »

Finally, the development of digital animation accompanies the emergence of research into 3D images: they feature common actors (Ed Catmull, for example, who was behind numerous advances in 3D imagery and was one of the founding members of the Pixar studio); they also share principles and tools (3DS Max, Photoshop...).

In this way, animation, born of a media transfusion from press cartoons to cinema, is in turn accompanying the deployment of transmedia logics, favouring an interactive and kinaesthetic relationship with the image. As such, it operates on multiplanar levels: technical, aesthetic, economic, cultural and social.

¹ KINDER Marsha, *Playing with power in Movies, Television and Video Games, From Muppet Babies to Teenage Mutant Ninja Turtles*, University of California Press, 1991, p. 6. cf. also HATCHUEL Sarah & PRUVOST-DELASPRE Marie, *Goldorak, L'aventure continue*, Tours, Presses Universitaires François Rabelais, 2018.